

ECG Arrhythmia classification: survey

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Abstract— Heart disease remains a leading global cause of mortality, emphasizing the critical need for detection early and continuous monitoring to reduce fatality rates. Electrocardiogram (ECG) signals offer a non-invasive means of assessing the heart's electrical activity and play a pivotal role in diagnosing cardiac conditions. However, accurately classifying ECG signals poses a significant challenge, especially with real-time data and standard datasets. This paper conducts a comprehensive review of recent advancements in deep learning methods application to analysis of ECG signal for arrhythmia classification. Various techniques are considered, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Deep Belief Networks (DBNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) and (LSTM) Long Short-Term Memory. By leveraging these sophisticated deep learning algorithms, efficient classification and detection of arrhythmias using ECG signals are achievable, marking significant progress in cardiac health monitoring and diagnosis.

Keywords— Electrocardiogram (ECG), arrhythmia, deep learning, CNN, RNN, LSTM

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause of death globally. Projected statistics from the American Heart Association indicate that global deaths attributable to cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) accounted 17.6 million in 2016. By 2030, this grim figure is evaluated to rise to 23.6 million [1]. The sooner abnormal heart rhythms are detected the milder the consequences and the quicker the recovery process. Electrocardiogram (ECG) used to detect the electrical activity of heart. Electrocardiogram (ECG) is used most commonly for clinical diagnosis in heart related disease due to its simplicity, low cost and non-invasive nature. electrodes are used to measure potential changes from different parts of the body tissue, an ECG is obtained and recorded with an electrocardiograph or a vector electrocardiograph. This process effectively reveals activity and abnormal rhythms of the heartbeat [3].

Arrhythmia is abnormal rhythms in the heart Any change in the normal heartbeat rate, like too quick heartbeat rate, too slow heartbeat rate, unstable heartbeat rate, or too early heartbeat rate, all of these symptoms can represent arrhythmia [4].

Arrhythmias, classified based on their origin, mechanism, and characteristics, encompass numerous types. The two primary categories are tachyarrhythmias, characterized by a rapid heartbeat, and bradyarrhythmia, which involve a slow heartbeat. Irregular heart rhythms detecting from ECG signals automatically is a main task of the automatic diagnosis of cardiovascular disease.

II. DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES

Deep Neural Network (DNN) widely used for classification and prediction purposes in different domains. Particularly in the field of medical, there has been a sharp development in DNNs, significantly enhancing accuracy in classification for numerous medical tasks. Modern Computer-Aided Diagnosis Systems (CADS) now harness DNNs to detect arrhythmias from captured ECG signals, resulting in reduced costs for continuous heart monitoring and enhanced prediction quality. With its strong ability in feature extraction, deep learning, as a computer-aided method, achieved accuracy high in the ECG signals classification. Deep learning utilizes the backpropagation algorithm to discern complex structures within extensive datasets, guiding adjustments to internal weight values across layers. This process fosters intricate fault tolerance and guards against misjudgements induced by overfitting.

A. Convolutional Neural Network

Within the architecture of a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), distinct layers such as normalization layers convolutional layers, , pooling layers, and fully connected layers play specialized roles in the feature extraction process and classification. The convolutional layers are particularly instrumental in extracting features from input data, achieved through convolving each sub-region of the input with a filter kernel. This process systematically analyzes local patterns, allowing the network to discern intricate features within the input. Each convolutional layer contributes to building a hierarchy of feature representations, where the j th feature map in the l th layer encapsulates a unique set of features extracted from the input data at that specific level of abstraction. This hierarchical structure enables CNNs to progressively learn and represent increasingly complex features, thereby enhancing their capability to accurately classify diverse datasets. [3],

$$c_j^i = \theta \left(\sum_{i \in M_j} x_i^{l-1} * w_{ij}^l + b_j^l \right) \quad (1)$$

where θ is the activation function and M_j represents the connectivity between c_j^i and feature maps from the layer. w_{ij}^l the weight (or kernel) for the j th feature map and i th filter index and b_j^l is the corresponding bias. Behind the convolutional layer there is pooling layer which performs a down-sampling operation to a block. Then it is used to reduce the features' size by selecting the most representative part by highlighting or suppressing features. the obtained features of each sub-region After the convolutional layers and pooling layers, then flattened into a one-dimensional vector as the input for fully connected layer. Mapping of different classes the input data is take place. labeled data and learning rate is used for backpropagation to update parameter with the cost function [3].

B. Recurrent Neural network

Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) extension, operates by sharing weights across time, making it adept at processing sequential data input and classifying time-series data for example ECG signals. Its recurrent nature enables feedback and present values to continuously influence the network's learning process, with the output integrating accumulated information from memory. In analysis of ECG, the sequential continuous nature of cardiac rhythms is pivotal for anomaly detection, RNN structures prove particularly suitable. They hold across time information, aligning well with the temporal dynamics inherent in ECG-data processing. Before categorizing identifying and arrhythmias, raw ECG signals preprocessing is essential. This involves cleaning and segmenting the data into uniform-sized segments, each representing a heartbeat or specific time duration. These segments are fed into the RNN subsequently as sequential input vectors, enabling the network to grasp the underlying temporal nuances of the ECG data. As the RNN progresses through the sequence, it discerns & extracts relevant features, culminating in the identification and classification of arrhythmias, thereby underscoring its utility in cardiac health analysis. [4].

$$h_t = f(w_{hh} h_{t-1} + w_{xh} x_t + b_h) \quad (2)$$

Where: h_t is state of hidden at the step time t . f is the activation function. w_{hh} is the weight matrix that governs the transition from the previous hidden state h_{t-1} to the current hidden state h_t . w_{xh} is the weight matrix that governs the transition from the input x_t to the current hidden state h_t . b_h is the bias vector. x_t is the input at time step t . The hidden state h_t captures the network's memory or representation of the input sequence up to time step t . the weights w_{hh} and w_{xh} are learned parameters determine that how information flows through the network over time. The activation function f introduces non-linearity to the computation.

C. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM):

LSTM is a type of traditional RNN designed for temporal sequences and long-range dependencies. Unlike simple RNN units, LSTM utilizes memory blocks, each containing one or more memory cells equipped with a pair of adaptive multiplicative gates for input and output. These memory blocks manage and update information across time-steps, governed by input and output gates that regulate flow of information out and in of a memory cell [5]. ECG data can be send into sequential data segments, allowing it to be inputted for an LSTM to arrhythmia classification and detection[4]. Each segment represents a series of electrical cardiac activities recorded for a set duration. This type of time-series data, comprising cardiac cycles sequentially, is then supplied to the LSTM, enabling it to model and learn the interdependencies among these heartbeats. Leveraging this acquired knowledge, the LSTM is used to identification and classification of patterns of arrhythmia, by making it a automated tool for detection of ECG cardiac arrhythmias.

D. Deep Belief Network (DBF):

DBNs :Deep Belief Networks constitute class of DNN where connections are permitted only between layers, fostering representations of data in hierarchical form. Typically composed of stacked Restricted Boltzmann Machines (RBMs) or autoencoders, DBNs exploit the arrangement where each layer's hidden variables works as the visible variables for the subsequent layer. Leveraging probabilistic modeling, DBNs unearth intricate patterns within datasets, enabling the construction of robust models capable of top-down generation and discerning high-level data abstractions. Particularly adept at tasks necessitating nuanced data analysis, indicating identifying hidden

patterns indicative of irregular rhythm (arrhythmias) in ECG signals, DBNs excel in capturing significant patterns crucial for detecting irregular heartbeats and arrhythmias. Nonetheless, akin to deep learning other paradigms, DBNs encounter a hurdle in the form of requiring substantial labeled data for effective training, a challenge exacerbated by the scarcity of labeled ECG database. [4].

E. Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU):

Gated Recurrent Unit is an improved version of LSTM with faster training process. It is simpler than LSTM with less computational complexity. GRU consists of gates that are collectively involved in balancing the interior flow of units' information. forget gate and Input gate are combined and formed a new gating unit typically called as update gate. The update gate mainly focuses on balancing the state between the previous activation and the candidate activation. The equations for computing update z_t , reset gate x_t , and the candidate activation h_t in a GRU Gated Recurrent Unit at time step t are as follows:

$$z_t = \sigma(w_z \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_z)$$

$$r_t = \sigma(w_r \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_r)$$

$$h_t = \tanh(w_h \cdot [r_t \odot h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_h) \quad (3)$$

Where: z_t is the update gate, determining how much of the previous state to keep. r_t is the reset gate, controlling how much of the previous state to forget. h_t is the candidate activation, representing the new candidate values. h_{t-1} is the previous hidden state. x_t is the input at time step t . w_z , w_r , w_h are weight matrices for the update gate, reset gate, and candidate activation, respectively. b_z , b_r , b_h are bias vectors. σ denotes the sigmoid activation function. $\odot$ represents element-wise multiplication [3].

III.DATABASES

In alignment with ethical considerations, many research papers opt to utilize existing ECG records sourced from online databases. Among the most frequently employed databases are PhysioNet, MIT-BIH, and PTB. These repositories contain labeled datasets categorized into normal and abnormal groups of rhythms, facilitating the training of Computer-Aided Diagnosis Systems (CADS). Table 1 delineates the prevalence of these widely used ECG databases, underscoring their importance as foundational resources for advancing research in cardiac health analysis.

A. MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database:

The most popular dataset for detecting arrhythmia is MIT-BIH, This database contain 2-lead 48 ECG recordings. These records collected 47 patients by MIT-BIH Arrhythmia dataset. ECG signal recorded for 30 min in duration, and there was 360 samples/second, with 11-bit resolution, digitization 10 mV. the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and Boston's Beth Israel compiled this dataset.

B. MIT-BIH atrial fibrillation Dataset:

The MIT-BIH atrial fibrillation dataset holds a distinguished status as a standard database for the detection and classification of Atrial Fibrillation (AF). Curated from collected data from 25 patients diagnosed with AF, this dataset comprises ECG recordings spanning a duration of 10 hours, each containing two signals. These signals are sampled at a rate of 250 samples per second, utilizing a 12-bit resolution, thereby enabling a digitization range of 10 mV. Recorded using ambulatory ECG recorders, the signals adhere to a standard bandwidth of 0.1 Hz to 40 Hz, ensuring fidelity in capturing the relevant cardiac electrical activity characteristic of AF[4].

TABLE 1 Arrhythmia Databases

Database	No of records	Duration	Diagnosis type
MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database[4]	48	30 min	Represent samples of Arrhythmia
PhysioNet computing in cardiology challenge 2017[4]	8528 train, 3658 test	30 s	Atrial fibrillation.
MIT-BIH Atrial Fibrillation Database[4]	25	10 hr	Atrial Fibrillation
MIT-BIH Normal sinus Rhythm DB[4]	18	24 hr each	Normal sinus
MIT-BIH Supraventricular Arrhythmia Database (SVDB)[4]	78 records	30 min each	Supraventricular arrhythmia

c. PhysioNet computing in cardiology challenge 2017 (AFDB):

AFDB dataset is used for classifying different types of arrhythmias which is recorded from single-lead ECGs, consists of 12,186 recordings, each lasting 30 or 60 seconds. The recording obtained from patient enduring mobile long-haul ECG monitoring and then it were gather by an online database repository, PhysioNet, utilizing the Alive Cor healthcare device[4]. The database is split into a 8,528 training set of records and a 3,658 records as test set with digitized at 44.1 kHz and resolution 24-bit using software demodulation, recordings eventually stored as 16-bit records sampled at 300 Hz, with a bandwidth of 0.5–40 Hz and a dynamic range of ± 5 mV[4].

D. MIT-BIH Supraventricular Arrhythmia Dataset (SVDB):

The Supraventricular Arrhythmia Database (SVDB) works as a important complement to MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Dataset, specifically enhancing its capacity to address the class of Supraventricular (SV) arrhythmias. Comprising ECG recordings 78 , each lasting 30 minutes, SVDB offers a rich resource for researchers. two signals sampled at a rate of 250 per second Each recording consists, featuring an resolution 11-bit for digitization. Notably, the dataset consists annotations pinpointing the onset of heartbeats (marked by the R wave of the QRS complex) and symbols indicating the type of heartbeat. Furthermore, annotations for signal and rhythm quality are provided, enriching the dataset's utility for deep learning model training aimed at detecting SV Supraventricular arrhythmias. [4].

TABLE 2 Arrhythmia classes:

N	Normal Beat[17]
L	Left Bundle Branch Block Beat[17]
R	Right Bundle Branch Block Beat[17]
e	Atrial Escape Beat[17]
j	Atrial Escape Beat[17]
A	Atrial Premature Beat[17]
J	Nodal (Junctional) Premature Beat[17]
S	Supraventricular Premature Beat[17]
V	Premature Ventricular Contraction[17]
E	Ventricular Escape Beat[17]
F	Fusion of Ventricular and Normal Beat[17]
/	(Pou) Paced Beat[17]
f	Fusion of Paced and Normal Beat[17]
Q	Unclassified Beat[17]

F. MIT BIH normal sinus rhythm database:

MIT BIH normal sinus rhythm database consisting of 2-lead eighteen ECG recordings collected from the patients between aged 20years and 50 years, this dataset comprises a demographic distribution of 5 men and 13 women. Notably, none of the individuals in the dataset exhibit significant arrhythmias. Serving as a standard reference database, it plays a vital role in the Normal Sinus heartbeats classification and detection, offering researchers a reliable foundation for studying cardiac health in individuals without notable arrhythmic conditions[4].

TABLE 3. Deep Learning Model ECG arrhythmia

Author	Database	classification	Result
Ullah et al. (2020)[12]	MIT-BIH	2DCNN	98.00
Peimankar and Puthusserypady(2021)[11]	QTDB	CNN-LSTM	99.56
Mahmud et al (2020)[13]	MIT-BIH	1D-CNN	99.10
Hammad et al (2020)[14]	MIT-BIH	DNN	95.30
Chen et al (2020)[7]	MIT-BIH	CNN-LSTM	99.32
Sharma et al.(2021)[15]	MIT-BIH	SVM+FFBPNN	98.53
Maidani et al.(2023)[16]	MIT-BIH	CNN+BiSTM	99.46
Kumar et al.(2023)[9]	MIT-BIH	Fuzz-ClustNet	98.66

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Ullah et al. (2020) and Peimankar and Puthusserypady (2021) have innovatively introduced models of deep learning in analysis ECG signal, eliminating need of feature engineering and broadening classification ECG include more classes. However, they emphasize the persistent challenge of accurately delineating ECG waveforms and the urgent requirement for richer and more diverse datasets. Similarly, Mahmud et al. (2020) and Hammad et al. (2020) highlight the data insufficiency issue in DeepArrNet and multitier DNN, respectively, citing susceptibility to noisy signals and data intensity. Chen et al. (2020) integrated LSTM and CNN and models for ECG classification, achieving high accuracy rates through increased subject diversity in training data, yet facing various challenges because of QRS detection requirements and imbalanced datasets, particularly affecting (AFL) atrial flutter classification accuracy. Addressing these concerns, Sharma et al. (2021) offered hybrid approach efficient for crucial arrhythmia classification, suggesting potential extensions to cover a wider range of arrhythmias. In a recent study by (Midani et al., 2023), recent investigation led by Midani et al. (2023), an innovative methodological strategy blending recurrent deep neural networks and feed-forward through sequential fusion is introduced, aiming to capture pertinent features of arrhythmias within ECG signals. Despite its promise, the study encountered limitations stemming from reliance on a relatively short database for both training and testing, alongside based on dataset annotation the use of R peak segmentation as outlined by Kumar et al. (2023). Notably, Table 3 outlines the classification methods for arrhythmia classification and detection between 2020 and 2023, with the MIT-BIH dataset emerging as the predominant choice for such endeavors.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Comprehensively this study reviews various techniques deep learning utilized for classification arrhythmia in ECG signals, alongside their respective accuracies. Notably, it concludes that among these techniques, GRU/LSTM, CNN and RNN demonstrate superior performance in classifying specific arrhythmia such as Atrial Fibrillation, Supraventricular Ectopic Beats and Ventricular Ectopic Beats. By synthesizing recent research trends, the study identifies critical components of the deep learning pipeline that necessitate further investigation before clinical deployment for ECG arrhythmia categorization. findings of these underscore opportunities for enhancing DL-based model for classification of ECG arrhythmia, thereby facilitating their integration into clinical practice.

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